

REINFORCED CONCRETE STRUCTURAL MEMBERS WITH FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER BARS (FRP): THE NEW BRAZILIAN DESIGN CODE

Daniel Carlos Taissum Cardoso, PUC-Rio, Brazil, dctcardoso@puc-rio.br
Claudia Maria de Oliveira Campos, Fluminense Federal University, Brazil, cmocampos@id.uff.br

ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) bars have been successfully used in concrete structures during the last decades. The corrosion resistance of FRP reinforcement is an advantage for overcoming problems caused by steel corrosion, improving structures durability in aggressive environments. Design codes and technical guidelines adopted in several countries, such as USA, Canada, Japan, Italy, Russia, aim to establish appropriate requirements for the design of concrete structures reinforced with FRP bars. This work aims to present the bases and methodology adopted in the development of a new Brazilian design code addressed to reinforced concrete with FRP bars. Some of the proposed recommendations are presented, including aspects related to ultimate and serviceability limit states for beams. Topics such as calibration of safety factors, strategies for ductility and combined use of discrete fibers and FRP bars are also discussed. The proposed code will allow safe and rational use of the material in Brazil.

KEYWORDS

Design standards, Structural analysis, Fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP), Concrete structures

INTRODUCTION

One of the great advances to improve the durability of concrete structures is the use of non-metallic reinforcement, in order to overcome the problems caused by the corrosion of steel reinforcement. Problems and costs related to the maintenance of concrete structures (Koch et al., 2016 apud Al-Khafaji et al., 2021), associated with proposals for more sustainable projects, contributed to the introduction of this new technology in civil construction. The main characteristics of these materials are their high strength, non-magnetic properties and low modulus of elasticity, very suitable for application in reinforced and prestressed concrete structures.

In the last 30 years, many studies have been developed on the behavior of concrete structural elements with fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) reinforcements. FRP bars are made up of continuous fibers (reinforcement) surrounded by a polymer matrix. The reinforcement can be made of aramid fibers, carbon, glass or basalt, and the bars made with these fibers are called AFRP, CFRP, GFRP and BFRP, respectively. Nonetheless, glass fiber is the most used type of fiber because of its availability and low cost, although the use of basalt fibers has increased in recent years (Empananza et al., 2021).

FRP bars have been used as reinforcement in concrete structures in construction and there are technical standards and practical recommendations for the design with these materials taking into account their different properties when compared to steel. Standards from countries like Japan, Italy, USA and Russia have been used for the design of structures with FRP bars and, depending on the topic related to structural analysis, different approaches are presented.

In Brazil, a new guideline (IBRACON/ABECE, 2021) was recently released and it was prepared by a technical committee formed through a partnership between IBRACON (Brazilian Concrete Institute) and ABECE (Brazilian Association of Structural Engineering and Consulting). The main objective of the publication was to provide good design practices and to pave the way for a future work focused on technical standardization in Brazil about the use of FRP reinforcement in concrete structures. In 2022, the Brazilian Association of Technical Standards (ABNT) created two technical committees to develop

standards for i) specification, qualification and quality control for FRP bars and ii) structural design of FRP reinforced concrete. The aim of the present work is to report some of the main outcomes and proposals related to the latter, focusing on recommendations for the design of beams regarding the ultimate and serviceability limit states.

INTERNATIONAL DESIGN CODES

For characterization and qualification of materials, the ASTM International specifications (American Society for Testing and Materials) have been widely used in the technical scenario and referenced in several design standards and specifications. The process of developing technical documentations on the use of FRP varies from country to country (Table 1) and technical standards and guidelines are usually established by specific organizations and institutions. This step is crucial towards spreading the material's use while defining reliable, safe and easy-to-use procedures for its application in real structures by engineers. The development of standards account for participation of manufacturers, designers, contractors and the community in general.

Table 1: Reinforced concrete with FRP materials: Some standards and guidelines

Code/Guideline	Title	Country	Year
ACI CODE-440.11-22	Building Code Requirements for Structural Concrete Reinforced with Glass Fiber-Polymer (GRFP) Bars – Code and Commentary	USA	2022
AASHTO GFRP-RC Guide Spec.	AASHTO LRFD Bridge Design Guide Specifications for GFRP-Reinforced Concrete	USA	2018
SP 295.1325800.2017	Concrete structures reinforced with polymer composite rebars (fiberglass reinforced plastic - FRP). Regulations on design.	Russia	2017
CAN/CSA S806-12	Design and Construction of Building Components with Fibre Reinforced Polymers, Canadian Standards Association	Canada	2012
CNR-DT 203	Guide for the design and construction of concrete structures reinforced with fiber-reinforced polymer bars.	Italy	2006
Japanese Society of Civil Engineers JSCE	Recommendation for design and construction of concrete structures using continuous fiber reinforcing materials	Japan	1997

BRAZILIAN DESIGN GUIDELINE AND FUTURE CODE

As previously mentioned, a guideline (IBRACON/ABECE, 2021) was recently released in Brazil. The IBRACON/ABECE Technical Committee on Non-Conventional Materials for Reinforcing Concrete Structures, Fibers and Fiber Reinforced Concrete, prepared a document based on international and national references, including some ASTM International standards for material's characterization. Considering the growing interest in the use of FRP materials in civil construction, the Brazilian

Association of Technical Standards (ABNT), created two technical committees aiming to initiate the standardization of FRP reinforced concrete structures in Brazil. The working group has taken as a basis, in addition to national and international standards and technical recommendations (Table 1), data from research that has been carried out over the last few years and whose data are published in the technical literature.

Materials properties and interface: general scope

The work that has been developed so far indicates that the general scope of the future code will take into account the following main characteristics:

- The FRP bars considered are those made of thermosetting resin, with continuous fibers such as aramid, carbon, glass or basalt and produced by industrial process that is recommended by the actual guideline. The surface configurations of the bars can be ribbed or sand coated;
- Aspects such as specification, classification and testing of FRP bars specific standard;
- The new standard will be addressed to reinforced concrete elements with non-prestressed FRP bars;
- Concrete used is that classified, according to NBR6118:2014, as normal strength (up to 50 MPa)
- Combinations of FRP and conventional steel bars are permitted, as well as the use of fiber-reinforced concrete for ductility purposes;
- Slabs supported by beams, i.e., flat slabs are not considered;
- Structures subjected to normal loading conditions, i.e., limit-states related to fire, explosion, earthquakes and others are not accounted for in the code.

Structural design: flexural design philosophy for ultimate limit state (ULS)

The design philosophy for concrete structures reinforced with FRP bars is different when compared to that used for steel bars. The structural member failure is characterized by concrete crushing (compression-controlled) or by FRP reinforcement rupture (tension-controlled). The linear behavior of FRP until its failure results in structural elements with a lack of ductility, a disadvantage that must be taken into account in the design procedures. On the other hand, compression-controlled behavior would be a more desirable for flexural members reinforced with FRP bars, since concrete crushing prior to FRP reinforcement rupture would result in inelastic behavior before failure.

In the design, the equivalent rectangular stress block is adopted regardless of the nature of failure. Then, the failure mode is determined by comparing the FRP reinforcement ratio, $\rho_f = A_f/bd$, to the balanced reinforcement ratio given by the following equation:

$$\rho_{fb} = \lambda \alpha_c \frac{f_{cd}}{f_{fd}} \frac{E_f \varepsilon_{cu}}{E_f \varepsilon_{cu} + f_{fd}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where A_f is the area of FRP reinforcement; b is the section width; d is the depth of the FRP reinforcement; E_f is the FRP Young's modulus; ε_{cu} is the concrete ultimate strain, typically 0.0035 for normal strength concrete; α_c is a parameter that reduces concrete strength in compression and λ is assumed as 0.8 for rectangular sections. The design strengths for concrete and FRP reinforcement are, respectively, given by:

$$f_{cd} = \frac{f_{ck}}{\gamma_c} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

$$f_{fd} = C_E \frac{f_k}{\gamma_{FRP}} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where f_{ck} and f_k are concrete and FRP characteristic strengths, respectively; C_E is the environmental reduction factor for various fiber type and exposure conditions; γ_c and γ_{FRP} are the strength reduction factors for concrete and FRP reinforcement, respectively. The environmental reduction factor will follow the same recommendations adopted in the ACI 440.1R-15, as a function of the type of fiber and

environmental exposure condition. BFRP bars were included with coefficients similar to those adopted for GFRP bars. Data found in the technical literature indicates that mechanical performance of FRP bars can deteriorate under severe environmental conditions (Al-Khafaji et al., 2021, Feng et al., 2022), but results have shown that additional research is needed for a better understanding of the deterioration mechanisms of FRP materials in order consider this influence in the calculation procedures.

Once the failure mode is determined, the corresponding depth of the neutral axis and the the design strength moment, M_{Rd} , can be calculated from cross-sectional equilibrium. The design against flexural ultimate limit state is satisfied when:

$$\gamma M_k \leq M_{Rd} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where γM_k is the design applied moment calculated by using factored loads as prescribed in NBR6118:2014.

Strategies for ductility

Some strategies are being considered to improve ductility, provided that they are verified by experimental results:

- adding discrete fibers to the concrete in order to increase concrete ultimate strain;
- by use of reinforcement that produces confinement of the concrete under compression;
- the use of steel reinforcements together with FRP bars and provide the formation of plastic hinges, improving the ductility of the structural element.

Model error and partial resistance factors

Experimental databases, obtained from the technical literature, have been assembled by the technical committee to evaluate the applicability of proposed design methods and to calibrate partial factors for various limit states. Considering the flexural strength data, Figure 1 presents the relationship between experimental moment and theoretical moment. Initial results indicate that, in general, the theoretical moment slightly underestimates the experimental capacity, but with a coefficient of variation of 17%. The calibration of partial resistance factors will be carried out using a Monte Carlo approach and considering the target reliability index between 3.5 and 4.0. The main random variables will be defined according to usual national and international literature (Santiago et al., 2019, He and Qiu, 2011).

Figure 1: Model error for flexural strength.

Structural design: serviceability limit state (SLS)

It is observed that, among the main methods addressed, there are many different formulations both for the calculation of deflections and for the calculation of crack width.

Immediate and long-term deflections

The Brazilian guideline (IBRACON/ABECE, 2021) adopted the proposed expression based on Branson's equation, also adopted by NBR 6118:2014, which recommends the calculation of the equivalent inertia, I_e . The methodology proposed by the Branson equation takes into account the effect of tension stiffening by means of the weighted average of the uncracked and cracked stiffnesses.

As pointed out by several studies, Branson's equations overestimate the member stiffness and then, underestimate deflections on the structural member (Bischoff, 2005). As a contribution to the new standard, the working group evaluated some of the main expressions proposed by others guidelines and standards. In the analysis, the expression proposed by ACI-440-15, based on the Bischoff's expression (Bischoff and Gross, 2011) has shown to be the most suitable method (Equation 5), given by:

$$I_e = \frac{I_{cr}}{1 - \gamma \left(\frac{M_{cr}}{M_a}\right)^2 \left[1 - \frac{I_{cr}}{I_g}\right]} \leq I_g \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where M_{cr} is cracking moment; M_a is maximum moment in the structural element at the stage deflection is computed; I_g is gross moment of inertia; I_{cr} is moment of inertia of transformed cracked section. The cracking moment is given by:

$$M_{cr} = \frac{f_{ctk,inf} I_g}{y_t} \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where y_t is the distance from centroidal axis of gross section to tension face and $f_{ctk,inf}$ is the characteristic tensile strength of concrete, estimated according to NBR6118:2014 expression as:

$$f_{ctk,inf} = 0.7 f_{ctm} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where f_{ctm} is the mean tensile strength of concrete.

The factor γ is dependent on load and boundary conditions (Bischoff and Gross, 2011) and accounts for length of uncracked regions of the member and for the change in stiffness in cracked regions. To simplify the process, a single equation for the factor γ (Equation 8), which is the result from integrating the curvature over the length of a simply-supported beam under four-point bending, was considered.

$$\gamma = 1.7 - 0.7 \left(\frac{M_{cr}}{M_a}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

The comparison between experimental and theoretical results (Figure 2), showed a good correlation between the results for loading levels corresponding to 30% and 60% of the ultimate moment and the single value for γ adopted showed to be an adequate approximation. As highlighted in the technical literature, the cracking moment is an important parameter for calculating the effective inertia. Thus, the suggestion for the new standard is that the cracking moment adopted (Equation 6) is different from that suggested by NBR 6118:2014 for reinforced concrete members with steel bars.

Figure 2: Theoretical deflection versus Experimental deflection.

The additional long-term deflection, due to dead load and that portion of live load that will cause a significant time-dependent deflection, is calculated in accordance with NBR 6118:2014, multiplying the immediate deflection by a time-dependent coefficient given by:

$$\alpha_f = \xi(t) - \xi(t_0) \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where t is the time for calculating the long-term deflection and t_0 is the time relative to the date of application the long-term loading.

Crack width

The characteristic crack width in reinforced concrete members with FRP bars can be determined considering the following equation:

$$w_k = \frac{2}{E_f} \left[1,5c_{nom} + \frac{1}{4} \frac{f_{ctm}}{\tau_b} \frac{\phi}{\rho_{ef}} \right] \left[\sigma_f - \frac{1}{2} \frac{f_{ctm}}{\rho_{ef}} \left(1 + \frac{E_f}{E_{cs}} \rho_{ef} \right) \right] \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where c_{nom} is the nominal bar cover; ϕ is the diameter of FRP bar; τ_b is the bond stress; σ_f is the FRP stress at service; E_{cs} is the modulus of elasticity of concrete and $\rho_{ef} = A_f/bh_{ef}$ with bh_{ef} the surrounding effective concrete area (Figure 3). The area is calculated considering h_{ef} the smallest value between $2.5d'$ and $(h-x_{II})/3$, where x_{II} is the depth of neutral axis for the cracked section. It is important to highlight that, when fiber-reinforced concrete is used, f_{ctm} in Eq. 10 can be replaced by $f_{ctm} - f_{ctr}$, where f_{ctr} is the residual tensile strength of concrete determined from a notched beam test for a crack mouth opening displacement of 0.5 mm.

Figure 3: Surrounding effective concrete area

Using the database, the experimental crack width, measured in the tension face of a member, is compared with the prediction given by equation 11. Figure 4 presents the relationship between experimental and theoretical crack width. Initial results indicate that the experimental crack width is underestimated in only about 3% of the cases. Therefore, the expression provides a satisfactory prediction for the characteristic crack width (95% percentile).

Figure 4: Model error for crack width.

Structural design: shear strength

The design against the ultimate limit state of shear is deemed satisfied with respect to the tensile failure of transverse reinforcement when:

$$V_{Rd3} = V_c + V_f \geq \gamma V_k \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

$$V_c = 0,6f_{ctd}bx_{II} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

$$V_f = 0,9df_{fbd} \left(\frac{A_{ft}}{s} \right)_V \leq 0,9d0,004Ef \left(\frac{A_{ft}}{s} \right)_V \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

where V_c is the shear force carried by the concrete; V_f is the shear force carried by the reinforcement; γV_k is the design applied shear force calculated by using factored loads as prescribed in NBR6118:2014; x_{II} is the neutral axis depth considering the cracked section; d is effective depth; $(A_{ft}/s)_V$ is the shear reinforcement area per unit length; f_{ctd} is the design concrete tensile strength and f_{fbd} is the design tensile strength of a bar considering the bent portion given by:

$$f_{fbd} = \left(0,05 \frac{r_b}{\phi} + 0,3 \right) f_{fd} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

in which r_b is the inner radius of the bent region, ϕ is the bar diameter and f_{fd} is the design tensile strength of the straight portion of the bar. The standard will also consider the case of slabs and very wide beams without shear reinforcement.

Model error and partial resistance factors

The working group carried out a study of some existing formulations for FRP reinforced concrete, with and without stirrups, and assembled an experimental database taking into account beams and one-way

slabs. The experimental results were compared with those provided by design standards such as ACI CODE-440.11-22, CNR-DT 203/2006 and CAN/CSA S806-12 showed both conservative and un-conservative results.

For the new Brazilian standard, the formulation presented by the equations was evaluated with the experimental results. Considering the contribution of the concrete portion, the use of Equation 9, and taking into account the results of structural members without stirrup reinforcement, provide conservative values of the concrete shear strength (Figure 3), with experimental to theoretical results ratios with an average of 2.51. Also, the experimental results considering the presence of FRP transverse reinforcement were analyzed, indicating, for most of the data, conservative results (Figure 4). The experimental-to-theoretical results ratios had an average of 1.32, with a standard deviation of 0.47 and a coefficient of variation of 35%. The calibration of partial resistance factors will follow the same procedure described for flexural strength, assuming a target reliability index of 3.8.

Figure 5: Experimental V_c versus Predicted V_c .

Figure 6: Experimental V_{Rd3} versus Predicted V_{Rd3} .

It is important to point out that the influence of the materials properties on each of the resistance mechanisms is still topic for future research, since it can be noted that most design specifications for shear strength are based on expressions adopted for reinforced concrete elements with steel bars. Also, some points of interest can be mentioned such as size effects and the addition of fibers to concrete, factors that influence the shear strength.

CONCLUSIONS

The work reported how some of the relevant topics related to the design of FRP reinforced concrete members are being addressed by the technical committee working on the development of the Brazilian standard. The error for the models adopted for prediction of flexural strength, shear strength, deflection and crack opening were presented and the procedure to calibrate the partial safety factors was described. Based on the results and on the researches that have been carried out on the subject, it can be concluded that the continuity of research work in the area will be of great importance for the improvement of design standards and technical recommendations. And also, such process will bring to the professionals more confidence in the use of new technologies in civil construction.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.